

Extraction of Thallium(III) with Liquid Cation-exchanger (Versatic 10)

SUNIL BARAN KAR and UDAY SANKAR RAY*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 285

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The distribution of thallium(III) between an aqueous solution and a high molecular weight carboxylic acid Versatic 10, diluted with butanol was studied. Thallium(III) was quantitatively extracted at pH 5.5 from 0.1 M acetic acid solution. The study of the effects of pH, extractant concentration, diluent and contact time on the extraction of thallium was performed. The probable composition of the extracted species was determined. Tl^{III} was separated from Ca, Sr, Ba, Co, Ni, Cd, Hg, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb and Dy. The interfering ions were Fe, Cu, Zn and Pb. The proposed method is simple, rapid and fairly selective, and can be carried out both at micro and macro levels. Quantitative separation of thallium from some of the synthetic mixtures are reported.

SOLUTION of versatic acid in organic solvents act as liquid cation-exchangers, the exchange properties of which are similar to those of organic ion-exchange resins. These liquid cation-exchangers have been used extensively in this laboratory for the extraction of di-, tri- and tetra-valent metals^{1,2}. Ashbrook³ reported the extraction behaviour of different transition metals with Versatic 911. Spitzer *et al.*⁴ studied the extraction and selective separation of iron(III) from copper(II) and cobalt(II). No systematic attempt has yet been made to study the extraction behaviour of thallium(III) and its separation with Versatic 10, hence the title investigation. The optimum conditions for extraction and separation have been carefully selected from a critical study of the various factors involved.

Experimental

The separations were performed in glass separatory funnels (250 ml) by manual shaking. The pH measurements were done with a Elico LI-10 pH meter.

Versatic 10 is a mixture of C₁₀ isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acid. The concentration and purity of the supplied acid is 5.32 M and 99%, respectively⁵. Versatic 10 was standardised by usual acid-alkalimetric titrations. Solutions of Versatic 10 were prepared by diluting it with butanol. Versatic 911 is a mixture of saturated tertiary monocarboxylic acids of C₉, C₁₀ and C₁₁ chain length. SRS 100 (equiv. wt. 260-290) is a high molecular weight synthetic carboxylic acid¹. All of them were supplied by Shell Chemical Co. (London) and were used without further purification.

The stock solution of Tl^{III} was prepared by dissolving thallos nitrate (E. Merck) (1.8 g) in deionised water. Thallos solution was oxidised to Tl^{III} by treating with bromine water followed by

boiling to remove excess bromine. On standardisation complexometrically with EDTA (disodium salt) using xylenol orange as indicator⁶, it was found to contain 5.3 mg ml⁻¹ of thallium. The chemicals and solvents used were all of analytical grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Extraction procedure: The procedure of the experiment was based on solvent extraction technique. The ratio of the volumes of aqueous and organic phase was maintained at 2:1. The aqueous phase contained 10.6 mg of thallium in 0.1 M acetic acid. Sodium hydroxide solution was added to adjust pH. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 20 ml, *i.e.* the ultimate concentration of thallium in the aqueous phase was 2.6×10^{-3} M. The solution was taken in a separatory funnel and equilibrated with 10 ml of 0.886 M Versatic 10 in butanol for 2 min by manual shaking. Contact time was varied from 0.5 to 10 min during extraction and back extraction. Distribution ratio reached a constant value within 2 min of shaking, therefore a contact time of 2 min was used in all the experiments during extraction. During stripping, contact time was kept 10 min. After equilibration, the phases were settled for 10 min and aqueous phase separated. To remove any trace of organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with 5 ml butanol. The resulting butanol extract was mixed with the separated organic phase. The amount of thallium present in the aqueous phase was estimated by complexometric titration with EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator. The organic phase was stripped with 2 M nitric acid (20 ml) for 10 min. Phases were settled and separated. The aqueous layer was again washed with 5 ml butanol to remove any entrained solvent present in the separated aqueous phase (acid extract). The amount of Tl^{III} present in that phase was estimated.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables on extraction :

pH: The extraction of thallium(III) with Versatic 10 was performed at various pH, at constant acetate concentration (0.1 M). The experiments were performed at fixed extractant and thallium(III) concentration. Extraction of thallium increases with increased pH and becomes quantitative at pH 5.5. The distribution ratio (D) and the percentage extractions of thallium(III) at different pH are given in Table 1. D was calculated from the extraction data using the relation $D = \frac{V_a}{V_o} \left(\frac{x}{100-x} \right)$, where V_a and V_o are the respective volume of the aqueous and organic phase and x is the percentage of thallium extracted.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF THALLIUM(III) AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Versatic 10-butanol (1 : 5)		Versatic 10-benzene (1 : 5)	
	Tl ^{III} , %	D _{Tl}	Tl ^{III} , %	D _{Tl}
3.65	78.1	7.18	31.2	0.9
4.0	84.3	10.7	52.0	2.1
4.5	94.4	38.7	54.0	2.3
4.75	96.1	38.8	94.4	38.7
5.0	96.5	55.1	96.5	55.1
5.5	99.0	198	96.8	60.5

Versatic 10 concentration : The effect of extractant concentration on extraction was studied by varying the concentration of Versatic 10 from 8.86×10^{-1} to 5.28×10^{-2} M. The experiments were carried out at fixed pH using constant concentrations of metal ion and acetate ion (0.1 M). Plot of log D against log [Versatic 10] produces a straight line with slope 1.6. Shigematsu *et al.*⁷ showed that Versatic 10 in organic diluent exists as dimer. Taking into account this evidence, the extraction mechanism of thallium(III) is proposed to be

where, the barred species are in the organic phase and RH represents Versatic 10. The thallium(III)/Versatic 10 ratio in the extracted species is therefore 1 : 3.

Various diluents : Thallium(III) was extracted with Versatic 10 solution in various diluents. The experiments were carried out with fixed amount of Tl(III) at pH 5.5 and volume ratio 2 : 1. Among the diluents tested quantitative extraction was achieved only in case of butanol having high dielectric constant value. In case of other diluents, like benzene, xylene, n-hexane, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform which have low dielectric constant values, extraction decreases. From extraction results (Table 2) it is difficult to relate extent of

extraction with the dielectric constant of the diluent. Butanol was used as diluent in all the extraction experiments.

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF DILUENTS ON DIFFERENT LIQUID CATION-EXCHANGERS

Type of liquid cation-exchanger	Diluent	Extraction of Tl ^{III} , %	D _{Tl}
Versatic 10	n-Hexane	91.7	22.0
	Carbon tetrachloride	95.1	38.8
	Xylene	88.0	14.6
	Chloroform	94.4	38.7
	Butanol	99.0	198
	Benzene	96.8	60.5
Versatic 911	n-Hexane	94.1	31.9
	Carbon tetrachloride	83.7	10.2
	Xylene	82.1	9.2
	Chloroform	95.8	45.6
	Butanol	95.5	42.4
	Benzene	81.6	8.8

Equilibration times : The contact time was varied from 0.5 to 10 min during extraction and it was found that contact time of 2 min was sufficient for quantitative extraction. Back extraction was done with 2 M HNO₃ (20 ml) for 10 min. Hence, contact time was fixed to 2 min during extraction and back extraction 10 min in all the experiments.

Different carboxylic acids : Comparative extraction behaviour of thallium(III) with different carboxylic acids as Versatic 9, Versatic 911 and SRS 100 has been investigated. It was observed that the extraction of thallium(III) in case of SRS 100 was less than that of Versatic 9 and Versatic 911. The results are given in the Table 3. The extraction efficiency of different carboxylic acids in butanol follows the order, Versatic 10 > Versatic 911 > Versatic 9 > SRS 100.

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE EXTRACTION BEHAVIOUR OF THALLIUM(III) WITH DIFFERENT CARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN BUTANOL DILUENT (1 : 5)

pH	Versatic 9		Versatic 911		SRS 100	
	Tl ^{III} , %	D _{Tl}	Tl ^{III} , %	D _{Tl}	Tl ^{III} , %	D _{Tl}
3.65	72.3	5.2	84.5	10.9	79.0	7.5
4.0	81.0	8.5	86.5	12.8	82.4	9.3
4.5	86.2	13.0	90.7	19.5	86.0	12.3
4.75	69.2	16.5	93.0	26.6	89.5	17.0
5.0	91.3	20.9	95.5	42.4	89.5	17.0
5.5	95.0	38.0	95.5	42.4	89.5	17.0

Extractive separation : The effect of diverse ions was studied under the experimental conditions. Of the cations tested Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} did not interfere in the extraction. The interfering ions are Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI}. The results are given in Table 4.

Separation of thallium(III) from synthetic mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical application, the procedure was adopted to extract Tl^{III} from some of the synthetic mixtures. The synthetic mixtures were prepared by mixing 5 mg of each metal ions. The results are given in Table 5.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON EXTRACTION OF THALLIUM(III) WITH VERSATIC 10

Thallium(III)=10.6 mg, pH=5.5			
Ion	Amount added mg	Source	Tl extracted %
Ca ^{II}	50	CaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	99.0
Sr ^{II}	50	SrCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	98.8
Ba ^{II}	10	BaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	98.7
Co ^{II}	50	CoSO ₄ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Ni ^{II}	50	NiSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	99.0
Hg ^{II}	50	HgCl ₂	98.9
Cd ^{II}	10	CdSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	99.0
Co ^{IV}	10	Co(SO ₄) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Co-extracted
La ^{III}	10	La(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Pr ^{III}	10	Pr(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Nd ^{III}	10	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Sm ^{III}	10	Sm(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Gd ^{III}	10	Gd(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Dy ^{III}	10	Dy(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	99.0
Th ^{III}	10	Th(NO ₃) ₄ .6H ₂ O	99.0

TABLE 5—SEPARATION OF THALLIUM(III) FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Thallium=5 mg, pH=5.5		
Sample no.	Synthetic mixture	Tl ^{III}
1	Co ^{II} +Ni ^{II}	99.0
2	Co ^{II} +Hg ^{II}	98.8
3	Ni ^{II} +Hg ^{II}	99.0
4	Ca ^{II} +Sr ^{II}	99.2
5	La ^{III} +Pr ^{III}	99.0
6	La ^{III} +Nd ^{III}	99.0
7	La ^{III} +Pr ^{III} +Sm ^{III}	99.4
8	La ^{III} +Pr ^{III} +Nd ^{III}	99.8
9	Nd ^{III} +Pr ^{III} +Dy ^{III}	99.0

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